

centre for population genomics

Garvan Institute
of Medical Research

OurDNA Browser Population Genetic Data Sharing: Multicultural Community Consultation Report

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Executive Summary

Overview

The Centre for Population Genomics (CPG) held a series of meetings in the first half of 2025 to consult multicultural community representatives on the OurDNA Browser. The OurDNA program aims to address the underrepresentation of many Australian multicultural communities in genomics datasets to facilitate more equitable access to the benefits of genomic medicine. The OurDNA Browser is one component of the OurDNA program and will be a publicly accessible database sharing summary data about healthy genetic variation.

With the Australian Multicultural Health Collaborative, an initiative of the Federation of Ethnic Communities' Councils of Australia (FECCA), CPG brought together the OurDNA Multicultural Consultation Group, comprising health advocates within multicultural communities. The group included representatives from communities of East African, Middle Eastern and North African, Oceanian, and Southeast Asian ancestries, which CPG is prioritising due to the lack of genomic reference data for these communities.

Consultation themes and CPG commitments

The discussion over three consultation meetings on CPG's open-access approach to sharing summary data on genetic variation centred on the themes listed below. Based on feedback from the OurDNA Multicultural Consultation Group, CPG is committing to several actions detailed under each theme.

Data Security and Privacy

- Including browser-specific security, program-wide data security, and AI-related concerns. CPG will:
 - Develop tiered data security information resources tailored to different audience needs
 - Consult with stakeholders if AI tools are ever implemented in the browser
 - Advocate for community-centred policies in international collaborations

Browser Longevity and Change Management

- Focusing on sustainability beyond OurDNA's current funding period, documentation, and future governance

- CPG will:
 - Develop and publish plans for the OurDNA Browser beyond the initial funding period (end of 2027)
 - Document change management approach on the browser policy page
 - Review governance structure and work with stakeholders to develop and implement a model that embeds community participation in the program's long-term decision-making

Safeguards Against Misuse of Data

- Addressing potential misinterpretation, deliberate misrepresentation, and response plans
- CPG will:
 - Develop guidance materials for users on the appropriate use of the data
 - Develop a crisis communications plan, including how to respond if the data is ever misused
 - Add a disclaimer on the landing page clarifying the intended users of the browser

Categorising Ancestry Data

- Concerning how ancestry groupings are determined and described
- CPG will:
 - Include an open-ended question in OurDNA registration to allow participants to specify their ancestry in their terms
 - Carefully consider how data is labelled to ensure that categorisation captures diversity within communities where possible
 - Advocate in international collaborations for data to be labelled in a way that captures diversity within communities where possible

Communication with Communities

- Covering how to explain the browser and its implications to community members more effectively.
- CPG will:
 - Develop multimedia resources to improve the accessibility of information
 - Create tiered information with appropriate detail levels for different audiences
 - Publish additional FAQs addressing likely community member concerns as identified by this group

Introduction

This document reports on a consultation process about the OurDNA Browser, a database of genetic variation that is part of the OurDNA Program. The OurDNA program is the flagship initiative of the Centre for Population Genomics (CPG). The program aims to build genomics resources that address the current underrepresentation of many Australian ancestry groups in genomic datasets. This underrepresentation is a barrier to the equitable practice of genomic medicine, which is increasingly embedded in routine healthcare.

Through the OurDNA program, CPG is partnering with communities of East African, Middle Eastern & North African, Oceanian, and Southeast Asian ancestries to address this representation gap and pave the way for a more equitable future in genomic medicine. Through these partnerships, CPG is building three resources for clinicians and researchers. These include:

- OurDNA Samples (a controlled-access repository of DNA, plasma, and blood cells)
- OurDNA Data (a controlled-access database of genetic and health information)
- OurDNA Browser (a publicly available open-access database of summary genetic variation data)

The OurDNA Multicultural Consultation Group

To ensure community perspectives guide the program, CPG has established the OurDNA Multicultural Consultation Group in partnership with the Australian Multicultural Health Collaborative (AMHC), an initiative of the Federation of Ethnic Communities' Councils of Australia (FECCA). Before establishing the OurDNA Multicultural Consultation Group, CPG presented introductory webinars in April and November 2024 to explain the OurDNA Program to representatives from AMHC's networks. Attendees from these webinars and others in AMHC's network were invited to submit expressions of interest to join the consultation group.

This consultation group comprises health advocates within multicultural communities, including those whose ancestries are underrepresented in genomics research and datasets. Individuals in the AMHC network from communities whose ancestries come from the regions that OurDNA is focusing on (East Africa, Middle East & North Africa, Oceania, and Southeast Asia) were especially invited to submit expressions of interest, ensuring representation across these regions.

Members provide feedback on critical aspects of the program, including approaches to data sharing, benefit sharing, and long-term engagement. In its initial phase, the consultation group focused on reviewing plans for the publicly available genetic variation browser (OurDNA Browser) and on helping shape CPG's approach to granting access to OurDNA's controlled-access resources (OurDNA Samples & Data). The OurDNA Multicultural Consultation Group's Terms of Reference can be found in Appendix 1.

The consultation group will play a key role in helping CPG to develop program-wide policies and practices that centre the needs of multicultural communities. While OurDNA works directly with individual communities to ensure their specific participation and recruitment needs are met, CPG aims to create a standardised overarching operational and governance framework that can efficiently allow the program to expand over time. There are dozens of Australian multicultural communities whose ancestries have little or no representation in existing genomic resources. This scalable model is designed to maximise benefits while preventing harm to participating communities, adhering to ethical best practices in genomics research with multicultural communities.

The approach developed with the consultation group aims to meet the needs of most, if not all, underrepresented multicultural communities and facilitate their participation in OurDNA. CPG acknowledges that individual communities may nevertheless wish to opt out of aspects of OurDNA's overarching approach. CPG recognises that communities bring diverse experiences and perspectives to genomics research participation and is committed to working closely with them through community-led approaches to develop inclusive pathways for participation in Australia's genomic resources. The OurDNA program focuses on Australian multicultural communities (also referred to as Culturally and Linguistically Diverse (CALD)), which, in the Australian context, refers to Australians whose ancestry is other than Anglo-Celtic or Australian Indigenous¹.

The consultation group members are:

1. Basim Alansari, Healthy Mend
2. Dr. Jerome Babate, Filipino Nursing Diaspora Network
3. Joyce Cho, Thriving Multicultural Communities
4. Sylvia Coombe, United Pasifika Council of Victoria Inc.
5. Abdisa A. Kalbesa, Oromo Youth Association WA (President)

¹ While not working directly with Australian Indigenous communities, CPG has partnered with Indigenous researchers through the ALIGN and CONNECT consortia to increase representation of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander communities in genomic datasets.

6. Dina Kerr
7. Naseema Mustapha
8. Dr. Saba Nabi OAM

OurDNA Browser: Overview

The OurDNA browser is a public online database of information about genetic variation in healthy individuals from diverse Australian ancestry groups. The resource will eventually include summary data about genetic variants (changes) that occur commonly in healthy individuals (without a severe genetic disease) in the Australian population. Summary data from OurDNA participating communities, starting with those of East African, Middle Eastern and North African, Oceanian, and Southeast Asian ancestry, will be added to the Browser over the life of the OurDNA program to build a representative reference of healthy genetic variation in the Australian population. This publicly accessible data will be used by clinicians and researchers to diagnose patients with a suspected genetic illness and understand the relationship between genetic variation and health. The OurDNA Browser will not contain any individual genetic information.

OurDNA Browser Consultation Meetings

On 6 February, 19 March, and 30 April 2025, CPG held consultation meetings about the OurDNA Browser with the OurDNA Multicultural Consultation Group. Across the three consultation sessions, the CPG team introduced and explained the OurDNA Browser and sought feedback from the group on plans for the browser's implementation.

In the first consultation meeting (See Appendix 2), the CPG team introduced the foundational principles of the OurDNA program, emphasising that genomic medicine should benefit everyone regardless of heritage or ancestry. The team explained how databases containing information about healthy genetic variation in the population are essential for equitable genomic medicine. The OurDNA Browser is modelled on the gnomAD browser, the largest and most widely used international database of genetic variation.

The OurDNA browser will make summary (or aggregate) data on genetic variation freely available to users around the world. This summary data combines information from many individuals and provides lists of common genetic variants in healthy people, showing how frequently each variant occurs in people of different ancestry groups. The team presented

evidence that this open-access approach would significantly increase usage of the data, leading to more rapid scientific advancements and clinical applications benefiting participating communities. Acknowledging the risks of an open-access model, especially around the possibilities of the misuse of data, CPG outlined safeguards to minimise the potential for misuse. CPG's position is that with relevant safeguards in place, the benefits of making genetic information from underrepresented ancestry groups immediately available for improving diagnoses and developing treatments substantially outweigh the risks.

In the second session (See Appendix 2), the team demonstrated browser functionality using the gnomAD interface as a model. This practical demonstration showed how clinicians could search for specific variants and view their frequency across different ancestry groups, improving diagnostic accuracy by providing population-specific genetic information. The browser primarily helps determine whether a particular variant is common in healthy individuals from the patient's ancestry group, which helps rule out variants as disease-causing.

The presentations also addressed consultation group members' concerns that arose in the first session about overarching data security and governance, including the separation of personal and genetic information, server location in Australia, and plans for long-term sustainability beyond the current funding period ending in 2027.

Initially, two sessions were planned but a third was added to explain CPG's future participation in federated gnomAD, a global collaborative effort that allows genetic data collected in different regions to be accessible through a shared platform. The team explained that OurDNA data is intended to be included in federated gnomAD, making the data collected in Australia accessible to people worldwide through this international resource.

The future inclusion of OurDNA data in federated gnomAD was initially thought to be a use case of making the data publicly available, since once released on the OurDNA browser, the data would be available internationally. Upon reflection, the team determined that the consultation process would be incomplete without including CPG's participation in federated gnomAD.

The team acknowledged that the omission of an explanation of federated gnomAD from when the browser was introduced was an oversight. Group members confirmed that federated gnomAD added an additional dimension to their considerations about the security of making the data publicly available and recommended that such topics be included from the start of a consultation process in future.

The CPG team explained the significance of gnomAD internationally as the global standard reference on healthy genetic variation. They described the benefits of global sharing of data on healthy genetic variation in different ancestry groups, noting that the data collected by OurDNA would have an impact outside of Australia. The team highlighted CPG's director Daniel MacArthur's founding role in gnomAD and his ongoing involvement with gnomAD on the steering committee, emphasising that CPG would have significant input into federated gnomAD's policies. CPG will ensure that federated gnomAD links to OurDNA's terms of use and guidance on the use of OurDNA data. Importantly, the team assured the group that OurDNA would only contribute data if the policies align with CPG values, and if concerns remain, contribution could be delayed.

Throughout all three sessions, consultation group members asked questions and provided feedback that have shaped CPG's approach to browser implementation and safeguards. For the third session, one group member who was unable to attend the meeting, watched the recording of the meeting and sent feedback afterwards. The areas of concern that the consultation group members raised were:

- Data security and privacy, including the use of artificial intelligence
- Browser change management and governance processes
- Long-term management plans for the browser beyond the funding period
- Ensuring that CPG is doing everything possible to prevent and respond to potential misuse of data
- Assurance about data accuracy, including the categorisation of ancestry groups in a way that captures diversity
- Effectively communicating areas of likely community concern in accessible ways

We go on to expand on the key themes that the consultation process dealt with and, in each section, outline the steps that CPG will take that are informed by the recommendations of the consultation group. The following section focuses on the areas of CPG action confined to the OurDNA browser and open access sharing of summary data of genetic variation. A full summary of the discussion can be found in the tables in appendix 3.

OurDNA Browser consultation meeting attendees

- OurDNA Multicultural Consultation Group members²

² Two group members were unable to attend the third meeting, with one providing input asynchronously.

- Nidia Raya Martinez, Senior Program Manager, Australian Multicultural Health Collaborative³
- CPG staff who participated in the consultation meetings were:
 1. Daniela Bodemer, Governance, Risk and Compliance Specialist, CPG Operations
 2. Samantha Croy, OurDNA Community Engagement Manager
 3. Zuong Dang, OurDNA Senior Advisor
 4. Saad Khalid⁴, OurDNA Community Relations and Strategic Communications Specialist
 5. Katie de Lange, Population Analysis Team Lead
 6. Chris Richards, OurDNA Team Lead
 7. Rafal Shouly, OurDNA Community Engagement Organiser

³ Nidia Raya Martinez played a pivotal role in the OurDNA Browser consultations and the establishment of the Consultation Group, inviting representatives from the Collaborative and the FECCA's network to be part of the group, advising on session planning, organising reimbursement for the meeting attendees, and supporting effective engagement in the consultation process.

⁴ Saad Khalid attended the first meeting as consultation group member and the subsequent meetings as the OurDNA team's new Community Relations and Strategic Communications Specialist.

Consultation Themes

Data Security and Privacy

Browser-specific data security and privacy

The CPG team explained that only summary data on genetic variation will be released on the OurDNA Browser. No individual genetic information would ever be publicly released. While individual genetic data is collected from participants in the OurDNA program, this information is processed to produce population-level statistics that cannot be traced back to specific individuals. This is the only data that is uploaded into the browser. These summary statistics show only how common specific genetic variants are within particular ancestry groups, sex categories, and age ranges.

Consultation group members queried where patient data would be entered on the OurDNA Browser and how personal information is handled. CPG clarified that the browser does not collect or store any patient-specific data. Clinicians using the browser enter details about the genetic variants they wish to investigate based on what they observe in their patients' DNA. At no point is patient genetic information inputted into the OurDNA Browser.

The consultation group asked whether access to the browser would be tracked. CPG explained that there are no login requirements to access the data to maximise use of the data. IP addresses can be tracked and blocked if misuse is suspected, though this may not necessarily prevent access to the data.

CPG emphasised that the risk to individuals of making the summary data open access is very low as it is not possible to link the data in the browser to details about participants. The only way someone could know an individual took part in OurDNA would be if they already had the person's genetic data and looked it up in the browser. Even then, the only new information they would learn about this person is that they participated in OurDNA and which genetic ancestry group they were assigned to.

Program-wide data security and privacy

While the consultation meetings focused on the OurDNA Browser and the summary (rather than individual level) data contained in the browser, the group had many questions about OurDNA's overall approach to managing participant data. Questions about data governance

and security emerged as a primary concern during both consultation sessions, with group members seeking clarity on how participant data would be protected, stored, and accessed.

Regarding data storage for the OurDNA program as a whole, CPG confirmed that all individual participant data is stored on servers physically located in Australia and would thus be subject to Australian privacy regulations. This is distinct from the data summarising genetic variation, which would be available on the OurDNA Browser for use globally. The group emphasised the importance of communicating server location in materials for communities, noting that this information would help build trust.

The CPG team highlighted the separation of personal and genetic information, detailing how participant demographic information is stored separately from genetic data, with no single person having access to both datasets. This separation significantly reduces re-identification risks and forms a cornerstone of the program's privacy protection approach.

Members inquired whether genetic data would be uploaded to participants' My Health Record. CPG clarified that OurDNA data remains separate from My Health Record systems and would not be integrated with individual healthcare records.

The robustness of the technical infrastructure was queried and more information about this was requested. The team noted that the browser would be open source, meaning all information about the code, platform, data analysis tools and so on would be provided in browser documentation. This would allow technically minded community members to be reassured of the browser system and allow others to recreate the OurDNA method if they wished. The group noted that high-level reassurances about the security of the systems, such as those presented to the group would be adequate for the average community member, while more technologically inclined community members would appreciate the more detailed information that CPG is committed to providing.

When asked about oversight of the browser development, CPG explained that multiple teams with specialised expertise are involved, including the Population Analysis team, who process the data, and CPG's software team, who oversee the technical build using open-source code borrowed from gnomAD, and who manage CPG's cybersecurity measures.

Security and Privacy Concerns Relating to Artificial Intelligence

Artificial intelligence (AI) and its potential implications for genomic data emerged as an important topic during the consultation discussions. The group explored both how AI might be used within the OurDNA Browser itself and how the open-access data might be used by external AI systems.

CPG provided context about the rapidly evolving landscape of AI in genomics, noting that AI tools are increasingly being used to understand human biology and predict disease. The team explained that CPG is engaged in research examining how AI can be responsibly used to benefit patients and communities while mitigating potential risks.

Regarding the OurDNA Browser specifically, CPG confirmed that the browser does not currently use AI tools such as large language models (LLMs) like ChatGPT to produce or analyse data. The team emphasised that they have no immediate plans to incorporate AI technologies such as these into the browser's functionality. However, they acknowledged that as the field evolves, such AI applications might become relevant to the browser in the future. A key commitment that emerged from the discussion was that if CPG were to consider incorporating AI tools into the browser in the future, they would first consult with stakeholders such as the OurDNA Multicultural Consultation Group. The group welcomed this commitment to ongoing consultation about technological changes as an important governance principle.

The consultation group raised questions about whether data from the browser could be downloaded and analysed by external parties using AI models. The CPG team acknowledged that with an open-access approach, they cannot prevent others from using the summary data in AI applications. The team reiterated that the summary nature of the information in the browser significantly limits individual-level risks, and that the risks are no different to the data being downloaded and analysed without AI.

The consultation also addressed cybersecurity considerations related to AI such as the browser or CPG's data management systems being hacked by AI. CPG explained that their internal systems include measures to mitigate the risk of AI hacking or other unauthorised access to data. The team emphasised their commitment to transparency about how people's data is being used, noting that they would continue to publish and consult on these issues as AI technologies evolve.

International data sharing considerations

In the third consultation meeting focused on CPG's participation in federated gnomAD, the group raised concerns about international users not being bound by Australian ethical

standards. The group also queried what risks CPG anticipated given federated gnomAD is US-based and Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion (DEI) projects are being defunded by the current US administration.

The CPG team noted that the data shared with federated gnomAD would be the same kind of data shared openly on the OurDNA Browser. The sharing of this summary data of healthy genetic variation would carry similarly low risk since no individual data is shared. The team noted that data would not be shared with federated gnomAD until CPG was confident that federated gnomAD's policies were consistent with CPG values. CPG's director Daniel MacArthur, who sits on gnomAD's steering committee, would be able to advocate within the federated gnomAD project for CPG's community-centric approach.

While the political climate in the US is unpredictable, the group was reassured that the OurDNA Browser would continue to operate even if gnomAD were to lose funding. A loss of access to a global standard reference such as gnomAD would be a major blow to the global community and remove an important resource in the diagnosis of genetic disease internationally. Nevertheless, the OurDNA data would continue to be available through the OurDNA Browser.

Based on this consultation, CPG will:

- Communicate server location in Australia in program materials for storage of individual-level data
- Develop information about security measures tailored to different audiences
- Maintain transparency about CPG's approach to AI in relation to the browser
- Consult with stakeholders before implementing any AI tools in the browser
- Advocate for OurDNA's community-centred approach in federated gnomAD and ensure that federated gnomAD's policies align with CPG values before any data is shared

Browser longevity and change management

The long-term sustainability of the OurDNA Browser was identified as a critical consideration by the consultation group. Members sought clarity on how the browser would be maintained beyond the current funding period and what processes would ensure its continued availability and relevance to communities.

CPG explained that the OurDNA program is currently funded until 2027, during which time all of the planned resources, including the browser, will be established. CPG is committed to establishing the browser as a long-term resource for Australia. The team acknowledged that planning is essential and assured the group that measures are being developed to ensure the information remains accessible in the future, even if the program does not receive continued funding in its current form. The group asked for documentation of these plans.

The consultation group emphasised the importance of documenting the consultation process and guidelines for browser changes to ensure continuity of approach over time. They asked whether formal documentation would be created to capture these aspects of governance. CPG confirmed that when the browser is released, documentation on the website would include information about the Terms of Use, expectations, and how changes to the browser would be managed.

Data update frequency was discussed as an important factor in maintaining the browser's relevance. CPG indicated that information in the browser would be updated quarterly as new data becomes available through OurDNA recruitment. Additional data will provide a greater picture of healthy genetic variation in each community.

The consultation group explored scenarios where the browser might transition to management by a different organisation in the future. They asked how CPG would ensure that community interests continue to be prioritised in such circumstances. CPG acknowledged the importance of this consideration and noted that developing sustainable community engagement models is part of their current planning work which they hope the consultation group will advise on in the next phase of consultations.

The group also discussed how changes to the browser functionality might be managed in the future. CPG confirmed that any major changes, such as the incorporation of new types of data or AI tools, would occur in consultation with stakeholders and community representatives. CPG affirmed their commitment to maintaining community participation in governance decisions. This commitment to ongoing engagement was welcomed as an important aspect of long-term governance.

Based on this consultation, CPG will:

- Develop a sustainability strategy (including exit strategy) laying out plans for the browser's future beyond 2027 published on the OurDNA Browser site
- Detail a change management approach on the browser policy page

- Review governance structure and work with stakeholders to develop and implement a model that embeds community participation in the program's long-term decision-making

Safeguards against misuse of data

The CPG team outlined the risks associated with making the data open access and approaches to mitigating these risks. Emphasising the low risk to individuals due to participants not being able to be identified from the data, the team focused on highlighting the possibility of risk of genetic data being interpreted or misrepresented in ways that could affect communities.

The CPG team presented two primary concerns regarding potential misuse of data: misinterpretation due to ignorance (making incorrect links between genetic variation and outcomes that are influenced by environment) and deliberate misrepresentation with malicious intent (e.g. using data selectively to support racist ideas). CPG acknowledged that while they cannot guarantee such misuse will never occur as data has been misused in the past, several safeguards already exist or can be put in place to minimise these risks.

The scientific peer review process was highlighted as an important existing safeguard. CPG explained that research using OurDNA data submitted to scientific journals would undergo rigorous review by qualified experts in the field. These reviewers can challenge false assumptions, identify incorrect interpretations, and recommend against the publication of questionable research. This process helps prevent the dissemination of misrepresentations through formal scientific channels.

CPG outlined their plans to provide users with guidance on how to use and report data from the OurDNA Browser. This would include information about appropriate research applications, methodological considerations, and strategies for presenting findings to minimise misrepresentation. CPG's Population Analysis team are developing these explanatory posts that will be posted on the OurDNA Browser blog.

The consultation group discussed how CPG should respond if data were misused despite these preventative measures. CPG explained their planned approach of carefully considering whether to respond to misrepresentations based on their potential impact. For isolated cases with limited reach, responding might inadvertently amplify harmful messages. In cases receiving significant publicity, CPG would use their platform as field leaders to

challenge misuse, draw attention to correct interpretation, and reinforce principles of responsible data use.

The CPG team emphasised their role as advocates for communities who have entrusted CPG with their data. The team outlined plans to consistently emphasise the partnership with communities in establishing the browser and to convey expectations that the data will be used to benefit these communities in the expectations laid out in the browser Terms of Use. CPG will encourage researchers to seek community input when relevant to their research and to disseminate findings back to communities in accessible ways. CPG will ensure that federated gnomAD links to OurDNA's policies and resources on data use.

The consultation group welcomed these safeguards. They recommended that CPG's plan to respond to misuse be documented in a crisis communications management plan. The group also agreed that communication around responsible use is an important component of the OurDNA Browser. They suggested that the team could potentially learn from past experiences of similar projects. The CPG team confirmed that they were keeping a close eye on developments in the field and that their approach to data sharing was based on learnings from past projects and the most up-to-date sector recommendations. An additional suggestion was to include a disclaimer on the landing page emphasising that use of the data requires skill and training.

Group members expressed concern about journalists potentially misinterpreting genetic data to create stereotypes about particular multicultural groups. CPG acknowledged this risk and explained how their guidance materials and response protocols would address potential media misrepresentations.

Concerns were also raised about pharmaceutical companies potentially harvesting data for marketing-related purposes. CPG clarified that while pharmaceutical companies could access the summary-level data like any other user, this data cannot be connected to individuals and has limited applications for commercial targeting. In the meeting about federated gnomAD, another question about the risk of misuse of the data by pharmaceutical companies was raised. The team reiterated that only summary data is shared with federated gnomAD. This data, on its own, while useful for eliminating hypotheses, is unlikely to directly result in the development of drugs for profit. It is possible that drugs will be developed using OurDNA's other resources, namely, the samples and individual-level data repository. These are controlled-access resources requiring an application and a process of approval to use. Researchers will need to clearly explain how the data will be used and how the research will benefit communities. CPG is committed to ensuring that both immediate and future benefits

are returned to participating communities. OurDNA's criteria for access to the controlled resources and program of benefit-sharing will be co-developed with members of the consultation group over the next 18 months.

Another group member, providing feedback asynchronously via email, queried how CPG will ensure that federated gnomAD complies with CPG's requirement to link to OurDNA's terms of use and guidance materials. This is something that CPG will consider over the coming months as part of reviewing its long-term multicultural governance structures.

Based on this consultation, CPG will:

- Develop guidance materials for users covering the appropriate use and representation of the data. These will be posted on the OurDNA Browser blog
- Develop a crisis communications plan for responding to potential misuse. Publish on the browser policy page CPG's expectation that the data is used to benefit communities
- Include a disclaimer on the landing page indicating that the browser is intended for use by trained clinicians and researchers who understand the limits of population genomic data
- Include consideration of federated gnomAD compliance with CPG's expectation in upcoming community consultations of longer-term governance

Categorising ancestry data

Having been shown data in the gnomAD browser with broad groupings such as Middle Eastern, African and so on, the consultation group queried how ancestry groupings would be determined for the OurDNA Browser. The consultation group expressed concerns about such broad groupings that might obscure important genetic differences within populations. Further, they noted that self-described ancestry may not correspond to genetic ancestry.

The team explained their approach, which combines self-reported ancestry information collected during participant recruitment with genetic analysis. When participants join the OurDNA program, they provide information about their ancestry (up to 2 ancestries), as well as their parents' ancestries. This self-reported information is later combined with genetic data to identify clusters of individuals who are genetically similar to one another. The team explained that they are planning more detailed categorisation, where possible, than what is currently used in existing browsers like gnomAD that the group observed. The specific

approach the team will take will vary from community to community, depending on what is observed in the genetic data and what the team learns from community members.

The team noted that they had recently started raising the question of how participants' data are labelled during their community co-design sessions⁵. Additionally, an open-ended ancestry question allowing more granular identification has been added to the OurDNA registration and consent flow in addition to the drop-down ancestries list drawn from the Australian Census. These additional practices are consistent with current recommended best practices in genomics, such as those laid out in the [NASEM guidelines](#) on the use of population descriptors in genetics and genomics research. The consultation group's comments have corroborated the need for this approach.

In the meeting about federated gnomAD, a question was raised about whether federated gnomAD would follow the US-based gnomAD's approach in labelling data from OurDNA. The team noted that they would be part of federated gnomAD discussions on how the data would be labelled and would advocate for labelling in accordance with communities' preferences.

CPG will:

- Include an open-ended question in OurDNA registration to allow participants to specify their ancestry in their own terms
- Carefully consider how data is labelled to ensure that categorisation captures diversity within communities where possible
- Advocate for data in federated gnomAD to be labelled in a way that captures diversity within communities where possible

Communication with Communities

The consultation group discussed several aspects of effective communication with multicultural communities about the OurDNA Browser. When discussing the appropriate level of technical detail to provide about the browser, members noted that while high-level information would be sufficient for most community members, a tiered approach that gave additional information to those who wanted to know more would be helpful.

⁵ The approach to this is evolving since some feedback from co-design coleads has been that asking community members this is, in some cases, confusing, and potentially also divisive.

The group discussed how community members would not necessarily understand what “open access” means. One member noted that OurDNA’s approach to sharing the summary data would need to be carefully explained for community members who wanted to know more. The team would need to take care to explain the program’s approach in a way that was accessible and did not cause unnecessary concern.

The group emphasised the importance of clearly communicating that the browser contains no identifying information. The third meeting further raised the issue of how to effectively communicate OurDNA’s sharing of data with federated gnomAD, noting that some community members would have additional concerns about this.

The group highlighted the value of multimedia resources to supplement written materials. A member specifically noted that some people may speak a language well but have limited reading proficiency and recommended multimedia resources for more effective communication. There were multiple requests for FAQs covering likely community member concerns such as data security and other issues raised by the group.

The OurDNA team acknowledged these suggestions and the importance of having suitable resources in English and community languages. With two new team members recently starting who specialise in media and communications, the team committed to more inclusive communication approaches and multimedia resources to engage with a broader set of community members. The new communications team members' approach will include more extensive use of community-based modes of dissemination, including community media.

Based on this consultation, CPG will:

- Develop in-language multimedia resources and dissemination approaches to improve access to information about OurDNA
- Creating tiered information resources with appropriate levels of detail for different audiences
- Develop FAQs, covering likely areas of concern including data security, explanation of open-access data sharing, and OurDNA’s participation in federated gnomAD

Conclusion

The consultation meetings with the OurDNA Multicultural Consultation Group have greatly enhanced CPG’s approach to implementing the OurDNA Browser. In addition to safeguards against data misuse, the group raised important issues of data security, governance,

international use, data categorisation and communications strategies with communities that will strengthen CPG's data stewardship.

CPG thanks the OurDNA Multicultural Consultation Group and the Australian Multicultural Health Collaborative for their time, expertise, and candid feedback. Their input will help CPG ensure the program has communities' interests at its core. This process of consultation is just the beginning of an ongoing dialogue with multicultural community representatives about the resources that OurDNA is building to support more equitable access to genomic medicine.

Based on the group's feedback, CPG has developed the following timelines for implementing the commitments the team has made to the group:

- Multimedia resources are already being developed to improve the accessibility of information about OurDNA. The new OurDNA communications team will continue to build OurDNA resources to effectively communicate with a broad range of community members

At the time of the OurDNA Browser launch in August 2025 [NOTE: this is the current proposed timeline for the launch, pending completion and approval of this report], these will be in place:

- Detailed technical information in OurDNA Browser documentation sharing in code, details of platform, and data analysis tools
- Browser policy page including:
 - Statement on data misuse stating what the data should not be used for
 - Expectations that data will be used to benefit communities and recommendations for working with communities
- A disclaimer on the OurDNA Browser landing page indicating that the browser is intended for use by trained clinicians and researchers who understand the limitations of genetic data

Q3 2025

- Tiered FAQs covering topics of likely concern to communities, including:
 - Specifying server location in Australia for storage of individual-level data
 - Data security details
 - Explanation of open-access data sharing

- Explanation of OurDNA's participation in federated gnomAD
- A crisis communications plan for responding to potential misuse
- A statement about CPG's approach to AI
- An open-ended question in OurDNA registration to allow participants to specify their ancestry in their own terms. This will guide the team's approach to categorisation of the data along the lines of community preferences

End of 2025

- Develop a sustainability strategy (including exit strategy) including plans for the browser's future beyond 2027
- With consultation group, develop plans for OurDNA's long-term governance that encompass OurDNA Browser and Federated gnomAD, including change management approach

2026

- Publish sustainability strategy (including exit strategy) on the OurDNA Browser site
- Plans in place for OurDNA's long-term governance for OurDNA Browser and Federated gnomAD, including change management approach
- Publish change management approach on Browser policy page
- Publish an interactive page of guidance materials for users covering the appropriate use and representation of the data

Appendices

Appendix 1: OurDNA Consultation Group Terms of Reference

OurDNA Multicultural Consultation Group - Terms of Reference

1. Background

The Centre for Population Genomics (CPG) is seeking to address the underrepresentation of Australian multicultural communities in genomics research and datasets through its flagship program, [OurDNA](#).

CPG believes that everyone should be able to benefit from genomic medicine which is increasingly becoming routine healthcare. Through the OurDNA program, CPG aims to establish and maintain respectful, long-term partnerships with communities to increase their representation in genomic data. This will allow the program to drive equitable advancements in genomic medicine that will benefit all Australians and ensure that the rapid pace of developments in the field does not lead to further inequities in health outcomes.

The program is building genomic resources designed to maximise benefits to communities through clinical and research impact while safeguarding community members' data. A key mechanism through which OurDNA ensures the program delivers on its commitment to better healthcare for participating communities is to work closely with partners from the Australian Multicultural Health Collaborative (AMHC). Through this partnership, CPG aims to develop trustworthy policies and practices for the program that centre communities' interests.

2. Purpose

The purpose of the consultation group is to provide CPG with feedback on OurDNA's policies and practices relating to topics such as data sharing, returning benefits to participating communities, maintaining long-term engagement and accountability, and alternatives to OurDNA's current community-by-community approach. Over the next few months, we seek input specifically on:

- a. OurDNA's plan for a publicly available, open-access browser that will share summary data on healthy genetic variation in different ancestry groups (Q1 2025)

- b. OurDNA's criteria and approval processes for granting researchers access to individual-level data and samples for research that benefits communities (Q2 2025)

These timelines may be revised and further consultation topics added based on a program needs assessment.

3. Group member attributes

Consultation group membership is by AMHC invitation. Members will be health advocates within Australian multicultural communities. The group will include members from communities underrepresented in genomics research and datasets, namely those of East African, Middle Eastern and North African, Oceanian, and South-East Asian descent.

4. Member roles, responsibilities, and meeting procedures

Members will attend consultation meetings as needed. These will be approximately five meetings in the duration stated under section 5 below. Meetings will proceed as long as an AMHC representative is present and at least half of the consultation group members are able to attend. Meetings will be recorded with permission so that we have an accurate record of the discussion. A CPG team member will summarise the key points from the meeting and circulate the notes to the group afterwards. Participation in each meeting is voluntary and members who cannot attend may provide feedback out of session if they wish by watching the recording and/or reading the meeting summary notes.

Once the consultations on each topic are complete, the CPG team will send a summary report which members will be invited to review. This report, which will be made publicly available, will summarise the outcomes of the discussion and will not contain quotes attributed to individuals. Consultation group members will be acknowledged on reports unless they wish to remain anonymous. Members may also be invited to be named as co-authors on any publications arising from these consultations.

5. Duration of the consultation group

Phase 1 of the OurDNA Multicultural Consultation Group will run from [REDACTED], focusing on the topics outlined above.

At the conclusion of Phase 1, CPG will, in consultation with this group, review the process to ensure it aligns with the needs of both participating communities and the OurDNA program. Based on this review, decisions regarding the potential continuation of the group will be made.

6. Remuneration

The OurDNA Multicultural Consultation Group members' remuneration will be consistent with AHMC's remuneration of community partners at [REDACTED].

Appendix 2: Presentation Slides

Consultation Meeting 1

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OurDNA Multicultural Consultation Group Meeting on the OurDNA Browser 6 February 2025

Chris Richards, Lead, OurDNA Program | christopher.richards@populationgenomics.org.au
Samantha Croy, OurDNA Community Engagement Manager | samantha.croy@populationgenomics.org.au

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Our Mission

We believe **everyone** should benefit from advances in genomic medicine

Millions of Australians are not represented in genomic resources

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Global availability of genetic data by ancestry group of origin

Underrepresented regions: East Africa, Middle-East & North Africa, Oceania, South-East Asia

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Our plan:

- to **partner with underrepresented multicultural communities** to **recruit thousands** of participants
- to **build and make resources available** for these communities that will:
 - Immediately improve diagnosis for genetic conditions
 - Improve prediction of risk for common diseases
 - Identify genes to develop of new therapies
- Starting with communities of Filipino, Vietnamese, Samoan, Fijian, Tongan, Lebanese, and Sudanese ancestry

Three representative resources - today's focus is the OurDNA Browser

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About the OurDNA Browser

What is the OurDNA Browser?

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A database containing information about **genetic variants** present in people without serious genetic disease i.e. a **healthy population**

The OurDNA Browser will:

- be **open access**: anyone can freely access this data from anywhere
- **not** contain any individual information or personal details

Definition reminder: A **genetic variant** is a change in a person's genetic information. Some genetic variants can affect a person's health or the way they respond to medicines or treatments.

What are some examples of how the OurDNA Browser would be used?

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Diagnosis

- A doctor observes a genetic variant that may be causing a patient's disease
- They check the OurDNA Browser to see if healthy people in the patient's ancestry group have it

Drug safety

- Researchers know a genetic variant causes bad reactions to a drug
- They use the OurDNA Browser to see which ancestry groups have the variant

What kind of data will the OurDNA Browser contain?

Summary data about genetic variation in healthy populations

- A list of the genetic variants that are seen in healthy people in the population
- The data is from many individuals combined together
- For each of these genetic variants, we will summarise things like, how many people have that variant:
 - from each ancestry group
 - are male or female
 - in an age range (e.g. <30, 30-35, ..., 75-80, >80)

Healthy population

Will NOT contain

- Detailed genetic information about individual participants
- Participants' personal information

What would data in the OurDNA Browser look like?

Data about this variant in South Asians grouped together i.e. 'summary data'

The age of people with this variant, compared to the ages of everyone in the study

Insertion (1 base): 1-55051215-G-GA(GRCh38) Copy variant ID Gene page Dataset gnomAD v4.1.0

Filters	Exomes	Genomes	Total
Allele Count	192	727	919
Allele Number	303936 *	152324	456260 *
Allele Frequency	0.0006317	0.004773	0.002014
Grpmax Filtering AF (95% confidence)	0.01436	0.01541	0.01552
Number of homozygotes	2	9	11

External Resources

- dbSNP (rs527413419)
- UCSC
- ClinGen Allele Registry (CAB71474)
- All of Us

Feedback

Report an issue with this variant

Genetic Ancestry Group Frequencies

Genetic Ancestry Group	Allele Count	Allele Number	Number of Homozygotes	Allele Frequency
African/African American	826	50194	11	0.01646
Middle Eastern	5	3076	0	0.001625
Remaining	26	16342	0	0.001591
Admixed American	46	42566	0	0.001081
European (non-Finnish)	13	226952	0	0.0005728
Overall	3	64578	0	0.0004646
South Asian	2	12814	0	0.0001561
XY	1	51764	0	0.0001932
Ashkenazi Jewish	0	14260	0	0.000
East Asian	0	14386	0	0.000
European (Finnish)	0	22994	0	0.000
Amish	0	912	0	0.000
XX	524	208704	8	0.002511
XY	395	247556	3	0.001596
Total	919	456260	11	0.002014

The label of a genetic variant

How CPG will address risks & promote responsible use of data

What are the risks of an open-access database?

Individual risk

- Participants cannot be identified from any data released

Risks to the group as a whole

- Negative storytelling about the data based on inappropriate interpretation. Due to:
 - Ignorance
 - Ill-intent

Safeguards against misuse of data

1. Peer review of scientific publications
2. Provide guides for researchers on using and reporting the data
3. Be prepared to respond if data is ever misused
4. Advocate for communities in the use of the data

Peer review process

- Anyone who submits a paper to a scientific journal will have their work peer reviewed
- Qualified experts in the field will read the paper and suggest improvements
 - Challenge false assumptions
 - Point out incorrect use
- They can also recommend that an article should not be published

Provide guidance on how to use and report the data

- CPG is working on guidelines and education for users of the data
- Guidance about:
 - The kind of research that could be done
 - How to present findings to minimise misrepresentation

Being prepared to respond if the data were ever misused

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- We don't want to draw unnecessary attention to negative stories
- If negative stories receive publicity, we will use our platform to challenge misuse
 - We are considered to be leaders in the field and our response would have an impact
 - We would use our influence to emphasise the principles of responsible use of data

Advocate for communities who have entrusted us with their data

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- Emphasise that the OurDNA Browser has been established in partnership with communities
- Convey expectation that the data will be used to benefit communities
- Encourage researchers to:
 - seek community input if relevant to their research
 - disseminate findings to community
- Share resources for working with communities

Consultation Meeting 2

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Second OurDNA Multicultural Consultation Group Meeting on the OurDNA Browser 19 March 2025

Chris Richards, Lead, OurDNA Program | christopher.richards@populationgenomics.org.au
Samantha Croy, OurDNA Community Engagement Manager | samantha.croy@populationgenomics.org.au

Recap: Three representative resources - OurDNA Browser

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Recap: What is the OurDNA Browser?

- A database containing lists of the **genetic variants** seen in healthy people
 - Contains only a small amount of data from many individuals combined together
- **No detailed genetic information** about individual participants or any personal information
- Shared freely to **maximise the use and impact** of the data (i.e. 'open access')
 - Clinicians use to diagnose patients
 - Researchers use to understand genetics and health

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Live walkthrough of gnomAD browser

www.gnomad.broadinstitute.org/

Recap: Safeguards against misuse of data

1. Peer review of scientific publications

And CPG will:

2. Provide guides for researchers on using and reporting the data
3. Be prepared to respond if misuse of data is identified
4. Advocate for communities in the use of the data (e.g. via Terms of Use)

Terms of Use - Expectations

- States CPG's core value of centering the people and communities behind the data
- Emphasises how seriously we take the trust placed in us
- Highlights the guidelines for responsible use of data
- Provides links to resources to support users to use data responsibly for the benefit of communities

What you told us

CPG's approach to AI

- Advances in AI technology are having a huge impact in our field
- CPG is a leader in the responsible use of AI in genomics
- The browser **does not use** AI tools (e.g. ChatGPT) and we have no plans to
- Because the browser data is publicly available, once accessed it could be analysed using AI methods
- CPG's data protection systems mitigates the risks of AI 'hacking in'
- Transparency about how we use people's data is important to us

Future Changes to the Browser

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Regular data updates

- Information in the browser will be updated quarterly with additional data from new participants
- Some data is better than no data, but more data increases understanding of healthy genetic variation

Consultation about any major changes in the future

- Sharing other summary data types (e.g. data about cells)
- Allowing summary data access through other trusted browsers
- We will consult stakeholders about any such major change

Learning from other projects and following globally recognised best-practice

We are keeping up-to-date with other projects around the world

And with what is recognised as sector best practice

We are learning from others' experiences e.g. recent controversy around how data is visualised

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Categorising Ancestry Data:

- We are consulting communities about terms used
- We have added a question to allow more specific identification
- We are avoiding approaches that reinforce misconceptions about race and ethnicity

Bringing new perspectives into OurDNA Communications and Engagement

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A warm welcome to Amelia Rahardja and Saad Khalid!

- Ensuring our **communications reflect the diversity of the communities we serve**, with inclusive language, imagery, and stories.
- Developing a **comprehensive risk and crisis communication plan** to help us respond swiftly and effectively in challenging situations.
- Improving the **accessibility** of our information to ensure concepts like "open access" are clear and easily understood by all.
- Developing **multimedia resources** to engage a broader range of community members

Amelia Rahardja
Media and Outreach
Officer

Saad Khalid
Community Relations
& Strategic
Communications
Specialist

Consultation Meeting 3

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Third Consultation Meeting on the OurDNA Browser 30 April 2025

Purpose of session

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To introduce **federated gnomAD** and gather your feedback

- Showed you the gnomAD browser - global standard reference database
- Hope for OurDNA data to be included in federated gnomAD
 - global collaborative effort to develop a centralised representative resource
 - allow data to have the most impact globally
- Need to include federated gnomAD in considerations for consultation to be complete
- Safeguards, guidelines, principles need to be carried over

Agenda

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- Recap of previous meetings
 - What CPG plans to do in response to group's feedback
- What is federated gnomAD?
 - What will CPG's involvement in federated gnomAD look like
 - Discussion
- Feedback on sessions
- Next steps

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OurDNA Browser consultation meetings recap

Recap on the OurDNA Browser

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- **What it is:** A public online database of genetic variation in healthy Australians from diverse ancestry groups
- **Content:** Summary data about common genetic variants across different ancestry groups
 - NO individual genetic information or identifying data
- **Design:** Modelled after the gnomAD browser
 - open-access approach to maximise data usage
- Approach that would work well for most communities to maximise benefit and prevent harm

Healthy population

CPG's OurDNA Browser Commitments

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- **Data Security:**
 - Provide tiered information about data security
 - Transparency on AI approach
 - Stakeholder consultation if AI is ever implemented in browser
- **Sustainability of the browser:**
 - Develop and publish exit strategy and change management protocols
 - Establish long-term community-centered governance
 - Consult stakeholders on significant changes to browser

CPG's OurDNA Browser Commitments - cont'd

- **Preventing Misuse:**
 - Develop user guidelines;
 - Create crisis response plan;
 - Add disclaimer on intended users;
 - Set expectation that data is used for community benefit
- **Ancestry Representation:**
 - Ask community members about best way to describe their data by allowing more specific identification
- **Communication:**
 - Develop multimedia resources;
 - Create tiered information materials;
 - Publish FAQs addressing community member concerns

Putting consultation group's recommendations into action

Data misuse statement drafted:

- Explains the limitations of the data
- Explicitly states what the data should **not** be used for:
 - E.g. "Infer that certain populations have greater or lesser predisposition to specific traits based on allele frequencies alone"
- Includes statement about intended users:
 - "This resource is designed for researchers and clinicians with formal training in genetics and genomics who understand the limitations of population genetic data."

CLARIFICATION: while we will block IP addresses in cases of misuse, this will not necessarily prevent further access

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Federated gnomAD

The gnomAD browser

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- Global standard reference on genetic variation
- Used in Australia and around the world
- Initiative of the Broad Institute of MIT & Harvard
- Established by CPG's director, Daniel MacArthur
- US-based and thus representative of US populations

Federated gnomAD: a global effort to improve representation

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- Underrepresentation of many ancestry groups is a global problem
- Data contributed to OurDNA can improve healthcare globally
- Data collected overseas will also benefit Australian communities
- Centralised database will ensure that people around the world benefit from efforts to address underrepresentation
- Will allow OurDNA data to have greatest impact

What CPG's participation in Federated gnomAD would look like

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- Participating projects follow gnomAD quality checks
 - allows data to be combined with data from around the world
- Federated gnomAD users will be able download data that contains OurDNA data
 - this data is combined with other global data
- Option to allow users to download OurDNA data only
 - alternative to require them to access this data via the OurDNA browser

What kind of input will CPG have in how federated gnomAD is set up?

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- CPG, along with other centres in Africa, Asia, Europe, and the Middle-East will have a say in how federated gnomAD is set up
- Daniel MacArthur (CPG's Director) is on gnomAD's steering committee
 - can advocate for policies that are in line with OurDNA's community-centric approach
- CPG will ensure Federated gnomAD links to OurDNA policies and guidance posts
- CPG will only agree to contribute data if federated gnomAD's policies align with our approach
 - We can hold off contributing data until concerns are addressed

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Your feedback on the consultation meetings

Help us make our consultation meetings better

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- What have you found helpful during our meetings?
- What could we improve?
- Do we provide enough information or too much?
- What else would be helpful for you?
 - e.g. more webinars? other things?

Next steps

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- Full report for review week of 12 May
 - Reviewed by group by 30 May
- Extend ToR until end of Q3
- Consultation meetings on individual level data sharing

Thank you for your input!

Appendix 3: Summary table of meeting discussions

Topic	Questions and concerns	CPG Response	Suggestions
Meeting 1			
Terms of reference	Additions to ToR		Add info about quorum, who will chair, who will take minutes
General	Other browsers		Learn from previous experiences and not make the same mistakes
	Consumer concerns		Add consumer concerns to FAQ and Terms of Use
	Why create new browser when others exist?	CPG control allows quality control, local governance, and ability to respond to misuse	
Data quality and collection	How are genetic ancestry groups defined and categorised?	Combines self-reported ancestry during consent with genetic analysis. Need around 20 people per group before including in aggregate resource. Groups based on both self-identification and genetic	Consider groupings and naming

Topic	Questions and concerns	CPG Response	Suggestions
		patterns.	
	Concern about broader groupings, subpopulations and specific conditions	CPG is planning more detailed categorisation than what you see in the gnomAD browser, but will need enough individuals to make summary data.	Consider groupings and naming
	Would data collection be recorded by location and would small groups be identifiable?	Location data not used for ancestry categorisation. Based on self-reported ancestry and genetic background. Will need enough people from a group to be sure people would not be identifiable. Data will not be released if this is not assured.	
Access to data and security	How will access be tracked?	No registration is required so names and affiliation are not collected. Only IP address tracking possible.	
	What about technology infrastructure?	All infrastructure information will be open source and accessible.	Document technical infrastructure clearly

Topic	Questions and concerns	CPG Response	Suggestions
	More comprehensive coverage of cybersecurity concerns	CPG has high security standards but we can provide more detail about this on the browser	Provide more detail about cybersecurity measures
	Pharmaceutical company access and data harvesting for marketing	Since anyone can access the data, pharma companies and others will be able to as well. There would be limited applications of the summary data.	
	Data being uploaded into AI	Cannot control this as browser will be open access	
Implementation	AI integration	No current AI technologies involved in browser. CPG controls information through processing pipelines.	
	Future inclusion of AI in browser and other changes to the browser	CPG is involved in work around the use of AI in genomics including work with consumers around thoughts about its use	Have guidelines and governance policies around future changes to browser
	Interface limitations	Basic interface shows community numbers, sex, and age range data needed by clinicians and researchers.	

Topic	Questions and concerns	CPG Response	Suggestions
Communication and risk management	Media stereotyping risks	Will respond selectively to misuse. Won't respond to fringe groups to avoid amplifying message, but will challenge significant negative stories.	Address misconceptions through engagement of science communicators/fact checkers to explain genetic information from a community perspective. Have an issues or crisis communication plan.
	Open access explanation	Acknowledged need for better communication about open access. Working to balance right amount of information when recruiting, and having resources with detailed information for those who want it.	Create explanatory materials in multiple formats
	Graphic is inclusive but it will be good if disability is captured in it as well		Ensure inclusive representation including disability in promotional materials

Topic	Questions and concerns	CPG Response	Suggestions
	Political buy-in and chance of being either positive and negative news story	OurDNA's aim resonates with communities and we have had positive coverage in community media; have government support via funding; backlash against DEI in US is something CPG is thinking about how to manage with increasing profile	
Community engagement and recruitment	Resource accessibility for different groups within communities	Current materials are mainly textual. Multimedia resources in pipeline.	Ensure diverse accessibility options
	Ensuring East African representation	SC response via email: We plan to start working with the Sudanese and South Sudanese communities this year, but we hope to work with other East African communities soon.	

Topic	Questions and concerns	CPG Response	Suggestions
	How will participation be acknowledged and compensated?	Participation is completely voluntary with consent required. Those not comfortable will not be included. Participants receive reimbursement for blood donation time. Use of data requires acknowledgment of source. Working on ensuring data use benefits communities	
Meeting 2			
Browser Functionality	Where are patient data entry points located in the system?	The OurDNA browser doesn't collect or store patient-specific data. Clinicians can only enter details about variants of interest. There is no input or storage of participant names, identifying details, or medical records.	

Topic	Questions and concerns	CPG Response	Suggestions
	Where is participant data captured or entered?	When people are recruited into the program, data is stored on a server in Australia. This is not connected to the OurDNA Browser. Genetic information is kept separate from personal details. CPG's Population Analysis team processes participants' genetic data to produce summary information. This is the only information uploaded to the Browser.	Important to emphasise that the browser contains no identifying information. Individual-level information (genetic and personal) is separate from the browser data.
	Can this info be found on myHealthRecord or will it be uploaded there?	No, only summary data is in the browser. No individual participant data is shared.	
	Can data be exported to Excel sheets for statistical purposes?	Yes, backend export functionality is possible.	
	Can you download all variants in the dataset or does it need to be done individually?	It's possible to download all the data which is needed for research purposes.	

Topic	Questions and concerns	CPG Response	Suggestions
	Potential for overreliance on genetic variants lacking strong clinical evidence. May need disclaimers about limitations of genetic data interpretation.	Very important point and CPG is already drafting a blog post to address this point. Doctors need additional data to make an interpretation.	In addition to planned blog posts, include clear disclaimer that browser is intended for professionals with training.
	Can doctors look up other variables if they are faced with a rare case with unfamiliar symptoms?	They still need to have an idea of a variant that might be relevant to the patient. They need to have a hypothesis to meaningfully use the browser.	
Participant Engagement	Do you give genetic summary reports to participants who are recruited?	When participants join the program, they are asked if they wish to be informed if their genetic data reveals a potential health risk. If significant findings are identified, we contact participants directly if they've consented to notification and guide them toward clinical services for follow-up testing. They can also request their raw genomic information and we talk them through the implications of receiving this.	

Topic	Questions and concerns	CPG Response	Suggestions
	What are the criteria for participant recruitment?	Participants must be 18+ years, identify as belonging to one of the ancestry groups we are currently recruiting, live in NSW or Victoria for now, have Medicare. Focus on recruiting from healthy population (no family history of severe genetic conditions like cystic fibrosis or muscular dystrophy).	
	Are there any incentives for participants?	\$100 gift card for taking part in OurDNA.	
Ancestry Determinations	How are genetic ancestry groups determined?	CPG is aiming for more specific groupings than what is observed in the gnomAD browser. CPG is looking to improve this through community consultation and additional ancestry questions. Data can be mapped to see how individuals are related to one another, coupled with self-reported data at recruitment. Can infer clusters and identify relevant groups.	

Topic	Questions and concerns	CPG Response	Suggestions
	When selecting ancestry, can you select multiple ancestries?	Need one parent to identify with ancestry. Can have up to 2 ancestries. Also ask what mother and father ancestry was.	
Access and Security	How is access to the OurDNA Browser controlled?	Browser is designed as open-access to ensure clinicians and researchers worldwide can access to increase impact. While there is no login barrier, IP addresses can be tracked if necessary.	
	Who is overseeing creation of the OurDNA browser and the underlying technology?	Multiple teams with different expertise: OurDNA team (engagement, recruitment, collection), Katie's team (population analysis and data processing), CPG software team (technical build). All browser data and code is open source.	

Topic	Questions and concerns	CPG Response	Suggestions
	For the average person, high-level security information is sufficient. Others might ask for more detailed information about security measures and technology.	The OurDNA Browser is fully open source. CPG will share the code used to build the browser, as well as information on the platforms and tools used.	
	Is it important to note that servers are in Australia?	All physical servers are based in Australia. Summary data in the OurDNA browser will be available anywhere in the world.	Emphasise server location in Australia in communications
Browser Longevity	What about the longevity of the Browser? Who will maintain it?	The OurDNA program is funded until 2027. Plans are in development to ensure information remains accessible into the future even if funding doesn't continue and that community interests remain central.	Document consultation process, guidelines for browser changes, and exit strategy
	Is the consultation process and guidelines for browser changes documented?	Documentation on website about Terms of Reference, expectations, and how changes are managed will be available on browser.	Develop comprehensive governance documentation and ensure this is publicly accessible beyond the Consultation Group.

Topic	Questions and concerns	CPG Response	Suggestions
	Sample size for Filipino community seems small. Could a limited sample size limit accuracy of the data?	100 is small but will grow (600 recruited so far with aim of 1000). Within the 100, very frequently occurring variants will be clear. The data is accurate but we need to recruit more to see less frequently occurring variants.	
Communication Strategy	Are there plans for a forum similar to gnomAD? This could be where negative interpretation comes in and will need to be moderated.	No forums planned, but ways to contact CPG will be available. Blog posts explaining appropriate use of data will be one way to prevent misuse of data.	
	Questions about privacy and security of data		Create FAQs emphasising privacy and Australian-based operations
	Would a communication strategy for communities and another for researchers/users be beneficial?	Population Analysis and Communications team are working on this. Explainers planned for both community members and researchers.	Develop separate communication plans for different audiences

Topic	Questions and concerns	CPG Response	Suggestions
Global Context	If only targeting Australian communities, why is the data being made publicly accessible?	Australian genomic data is impactful globally. Information is valuable for people of the same ancestry no matter where they are located.	
	Can we obtain data of target communities from other countries? What is the desired sample size?	Focus is on creating an Australian resource with consistent analysis methods. Desired sample size approximately 1000 per community, adjusting based on what's observed in the data. If data is collected by researchers overseas and shared publicly in the same way that OurDNA is doing, this will also benefit communities in Australia.	
Meeting 3			
Federated gnomAD governance			

Topic	Questions and concerns	CPG Response	Suggestions
	<p>Who has the IP of the data once it is included in federated gnomAD?</p>	<p>The data shared with gnomAD will be the same summary information shared on the OurDNA Browser. While CPG are the custodians of the data, there is no IP attached to it. Once OurDNA data is merged into gnomAD, it will be part of a larger dataset and will not be distinguishable as "OurDNA data."</p>	
	<p>What standards will CPG apply if pharmaceutical and medical devices companies using the data aren't held to Australian ethical frameworks?</p>	<p>For the Browser summary data which is publicly accessible, CPG is not able to enforce standards beyond laying out expectation in the browser policy. For the individual-level data, researchers will need to explain how they will use the data and meet certain criteria including demonstrating their research will benefit communities, and gaining ethics approval for their research.</p>	<p>While we can't stop people from misusing data, we should think about how we can do our best to minimise harm.</p>

Topic	Questions and concerns	CPG Response	Suggestions
	<p>How will compliance will be monitored to ensure that Federated gnomAD links to OurDNA policies and guidance?*</p> <p>[Asynchronous feedback]</p>	<p>This as a good question that requires some thought. We can explore this further as we review ongoing multicultural governance for OurDNA.</p>	<p>Add federated gnomAD considerations to questions of ongoing governance.</p>
Funding	<p>Could the defunding of DEI initiatives in the current US political climate be a risk in sharing OurDNA data with federated gnomAD?</p>	<p>OurDNA is funded independently from gnomAD. The defunding of DEI initiatives in the US is a significant concern. Defunding of gnomAD would be a major loss of a global standard reference and the ability to diagnose genetic illnesses. The OurDNA resources will continue to be available independent of gnomAD funding.</p>	
	<p>The Broad is based at Harvard. How might the Trump administration's feud with Harvard affect the program?</p>	<p>CPG has collaborations with the Broad and groups like Microsoft that work on other areas of the centres work. The funding cuts to research in the US are a concern though most of CPG's funding is from Australian sources.</p>	

Topic	Questions and concerns	CPG Response	Suggestions
Genetic similiarity	What are the challenges to identifying healthy DNA variation since there is a high level of genetic similarity?	Human DNA sequences are majority identical. We are all very, very similar. But there are still 3 billion positions in that genome where little changes can happen. There is a lot of genetic variation but it is a tiny fraction of the complete DNA.	
OurDNA Browser policies	Are we required to contribute to the draft policy on data misuse as part of this consultation process?	The policy is very technical and aimed at database users, but the team can extract relevant parts and share them with the group if there's interest.	Share relevant parts of OurDNA policies with consultation group.
Global data on healthy genetic variation	Why is the US not shown as a collaborator in federated gnomAD?	gnomAD is based in the US—they're trying to diversify it through global contributions. The federated gnomAD page is misleading as the US and UK data that makes up the bulk of the current gnomAD data is not represented. This would be good feedback for CPG to give to federated gnomAD.	

Topic	Questions and concerns	CPG Response	Suggestions
	Will classifications of ancestry differ globally? How will data be represented in federated gnomAD?	The example we showed in the gnomAD browser was US-centric, but CPG will have input into how the data is labelled. We can provide feedback to gnomAD based on what we learn from communities about their preferences.	
	Would East African DNA data be applicable outside Australia?	Yes, the data from OurDNA would be relevant to East African communities outside of Australian.	
Communication about federated gnomAD	It would have been good to have introduced federated gnomAD at the start of the consultation process.	The team acknowledged the oversight, initially seeing this as a technical implementation detail, but later recognising its likely significance from a community perspective.	Include all relevant information at the start of a consultation process.

Topic	Questions and concerns	CPG Response	Suggestions
	<p>Communities may have concerns about federated gnomAD. What federated gnomAD is and how data is protected</p>	<p>CPG noted that explanation of the browser would be included in the planned FAQ and would require tiered information.</p>	<p>A consultation group member suggested using plain language and visuals to help communities understand how the federated model works and how it protects their data.</p>